

A fluorescence study of 1-*p*-aminophenyl-4-phenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene in organic solvents, 1,4-dioxane–water binary mixtures and micelles

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1-*p*-Aminophenyl-4-phenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene (**1**) has been synthesized and its uv-vis absorption and fluorescence emission and excitation spectral properties in a variety of media including organic solvents and 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures of varying relative permittivity, and microheterogeneous media of SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100 micelles have been examined. In contrast to a largely solvent polarity insensitive nature of the uv-vis absorption and fluorescence excitation spectra, the fluorescence emission maximum ($\lambda_{f \max}$) and the fluorescence quantum yield (Φ_f) of **1** are significantly influenced by polarity of the medium. The aminodiene **1** in non-polar *n*-heptane shows $\lambda_{f \max}$ at 422 nm, but in relatively more polar solvents it shows two bands at 426–438 and 467–492 nm, depending on the relative permittivity of the medium. In general, as the polarity of medium is increased, the $\lambda_{f \max}$ of **1** undergoes gradual red-shift with decreased fluorescence intensity at the shorter wavelength fluorescence band and enhanced fluorescence intensity at the longer wavelength fluorescence band. Further, as the polarity of the medium is increased, the Φ_f decreases. The solvatochromic fluorescence of **1** has also been discussed in terms of the solvent polarity parameter, Δf .

In the micellar medium also, **1** exhibits two fluorescence bands, which appear more prominently in SDS micelles as compared to in CTAB or in Triton-X-100 micelles. The positions of the fluorescence bands are found to be dependent on the electronic charges of the micelles. Micropolarity of the solubilization site of **1** in various micelles has also been discussed and it has been suggested that **1** is intercalated in the interfacial domains of the micelles. In general, **1** fluoresces more efficiently in neutral micelles of Triton-X-100 than in ionic micelles of SDS or CTAB.

The fluorescence properties of **1** have been discussed in terms of the involvement of apolar, initially prepared locally excited state (in non-polar medium) and dipolar, intramolecular charge transfer excited state (in polar medium) along with the possible influence of the solvent polarity induced energy level re-ordering of the lowest singlet excited states of the aminodiene.

This study has brought out interesting features of the excited state structure and dynamics of donor-acceptor diphenylpolyenes and showed the importance of charge transfer excited states in the photoprocesses of linear polyenes in general. Additionally, it provides new directions for designing fluorescence probes as sensors and reporters of the microenvironment of organized assemblies.

Linear polyenes exhibit interesting electro-optical properties¹ and play important roles in biological photosensory and energy transductions². Therefore, the excited states of linear polyenes and related molecules have been the subject of numerous photochemical and photophysical investigations, excellent accounts of which are available in several articles¹⁻³. Particularly, the excited state structure and dynamics of linear polyenes have attracted a great deal of attention and have been the subject matter of much discussion in recent years. Currently, however, the exact nature of the excited states involved in the photoprocesses of linear polyenes is not fully understood. In this context, the significance of charge transfer phenomenon in the photoprocesses of linear polyenes and related chromophores has been discussed and it has been suggested that configurationally re-

laxed dipolar excited states can be involved in the photochemistry of these chromophores^{3c,h,4}. Additionally, the role of conformationally relaxed non-planar, intramolecular charge transfer excited states in the photoprocesses of linear polyenes and related systems has also been discussed⁵. Recently, we have investigated⁶ excited state properties of several donor-acceptor substituted 1,2-diphenylethenes and 1,4-diphenyl-butadienes and found that the nitro-substituted 1,4-diphenylbutadienes exhibit highly solvatochromic fluorescence emission due to polar excited state^{6a,b}. The fluorescence efficiency of the nitro-dienes has been found to be very low, particularly in protic-polar solvents. These fluorescence properties of the donor-acceptor dienes have been explained in terms of the involvement of conformationally relaxed non-planar excited states, which become dipolar in

nature due to excited state intramolecular charge transfer process. Additionally, the role of solvent-induced energy level re-ordering of the two lowest excited states of the diphenylbutadienes in their photoprocesses has also been considered.

Herein is reported a fluorescence study of a diphenylbutadiene compound, namely, 1-*p*-aminophenyl-4-phenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene (**1**, Fig. 1) bearing electron-releasing amino group on one of the aromatic rings. Thus, in this work, aminodiene **1** has been prepared and its absorption and fluorescence emission and excitation properties in homogeneous medium of organic solvents and 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures of varying relative permittivity (dielectric constant, ϵ), and in the micelles of CTAB, SDS and Triton-X-100 have been examined. It has been shown that the amino-substituted diene **1** exhibits solvent-polarity dependent fluorescence in which the lower wavelength emission originates from an initially prepared locally excited state and the longer wavelength emission originates from a dipolar intramolecular charge transfer excited state. As compared the nitrodienes^{6a}, the amino-substituted diene fluoresces more efficiently in protic polar medium. The fluorescence efficiency of **1** is more in neutral micelles as compared to in ionic micelles. Similar to nitrodienes, the aminodiene **1** is most fluorescent in neutral micelles^{6a}. However, in contrast to the nitrodiene, the aminodiene does not seem to involve conformationally relaxed twisted excited states in its photoprocess.

Fig. 1. Structure of aminodiene **1**

Results and Discussion

*Uv-vis absorption and fluorescence emission properties of 1-*p*-aminophenyl-4-phenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene (**1**) in homogeneous medium of organic solvents*: The uv-vis absorption and fluorescence spectral data of **1** in various organic solvents and in 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures are summarized in Table 1. The absorption maximum ($\lambda_{ab\ max}$) of the diene gets moderately red-shifted as the relative permittivity (ϵ , dielectric constant) of the solvent is increased. Thus, while in relatively less-polar solvent like *n*-heptane (having relatively low ϵ), the aminodiene maximally absorbs at 348 nm, in more polar solvent like aprotic DMF (with relatively high ϵ), it shows $\lambda_{ab\ max}$ at 365 nm. However, in protic-polar solvents like methanol, there is a blue-shift in the $\lambda_{ab\ max}$ of the aminodiene. In 1,4-dioxane, the aminodiene

Table 1. Uv-vis absorption and fluorescence emission data for 1-*p*-aminophenyl-4-phenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene (**1**) in various organic solvents and in 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures

Solvent	$\lambda_{ab\ max}$ nm	$\lambda_{f\ max}$ nm	$\lambda_{ex\ max}$ nm	Φ_f
<i>n</i> -Heptane	348	422	349	0.073
1,4-Dioxane	356	426, 467	359	0.041
THF	356	430, 461	359	0.036
MeCN	354	435, 474	356	0.028
MeOH	350	433, 473	350	0.022
DMF	365	482	365	0.030
1,4-Dioxane-10% H ₂ O	358	435, 467	357	0.033
1,4-Dioxane-20% H ₂ O	358	436, 471	357	0.034
1,4-Dioxane-30% H ₂ O	357	436, 473	358	0.031
1,4-Dioxane-40% H ₂ O	356	435, 475	356	0.028
1,4-Dioxane-50% H ₂ O	353	435, 479	354	0.025
1,4-Dioxane-60% H ₂ O	352	433, 482	352	0.025
1,4-Dioxane-70% H ₂ O	351	433, 485	350	0.022
1,4-Dioxane-80% H ₂ O	349	433, 488	350	0.017
1,4-Dioxane-90% H ₂ O	346	438, 492	345	0.015

* $\lambda_{ab\ max}$ = Absorption maximum, $\lambda_{f\ max}$ = fluorescence emission maximum, $\lambda_{ex\ max}$ = fluorescence excitation maximum, Φ_f = fluorescence quantum yield determined against quinone sulfate²

shows $\lambda_{ab\ max}$ at 356 nm. Addition of water in 1,4-dioxane does not significantly alter the $\lambda_{ab\ max}$ of the aminodiene. However, at higher water amounts in 1,4-dioxane, the $\lambda_{ab\ max}$ gets slightly blue-shifted. Thus, from 0% water to 100% water variation, a maximum of only 10 nm blue-shift was observed in the $\lambda_{ab\ max}$ of **1**. In general, the aminodiene suffers a blue-shift in its $\lambda_{ab\ max}$ in protic-polar solvents. This can be due to the presence of hydrogen bond interaction between the ground state aminodiene and the protic solvents. Such interactions can stabilize the ground state of the aminodiene more strongly than its electronically excited state. As compared to the unsubstituted parent diene, 1,4-diphenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene (DPB), which shows absorption maximum at 330 nm with vibrational structures located at 315 and 350 nm, the aminodiene **1** shows red-shifted absorption maximum in the range 346–365 depending on the relative permittivity of the medium, and the absorption band is devoid of any vibrational features. The red-shifted absorption of the aminodiene as compared to the parent unsubstituted diene can be attributed to the mesomeric effect of the electron-releasing amino group, which can cause greater delocalization due to the extended conjugation.

In contrast to a rather weak solvent polarity effect on the $\lambda_{ab\ max}$, a significant influence of solvent polarity on the fluorescence maximum ($\lambda_{f\ max}$) of **1** is seen. The fluorescence spectra of **1** in solvents of varying relative permitti-

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of **1** in (a) *n*-heptane, (b) 1,4-dioxane, (c) tetrahydrofuran, (d) acetonitrile, (e) methanol and (f) dimethylformamide.

vity are shown in Fig. 2. The fluorescence spectrum of the parent unsubstituted diene (DPB) is largely insensitive to the solvent polarity. In contrast, the aminodiene **1** in relatively non-polar *n*-heptane while shows $\lambda_{f \max}$ at 422 nm only, in relatively more polar solvents it shows two fluorescence bands at 426–438 and 467–492 nm, depending on the relative permittivity of the medium. In DMF, however, only one fluorescence band with maximum at 482 nm is observed. Thus, the fluorescence emission of **1** is sensitive to solvent polarity. The excitation spectrum (Fig. 3) of **1** is independent of the solvent polarity and is similar to the absorption spectrum. Further, the excitation spectrum of the aminodiene is also independent of both the emission wavelengths. The quantum yield of fluorescence (Φ_f) of **1** in organic solvents and in 1,4-dioxane-water binary systems decreases as the relative permittivity of the medium is increased.

To demonstrate the solvent polarity based gradual change

Fig. 3. Excitation spectra of **1** in (a) *n*-heptane, (b) tetrahydrofuran, (c) acetonitrile and (d) methanol.

in $\lambda_{f \max}$ and increase in intensity of the longer wavelength fluorescence band (i.e. 467–492 nm range), fluorescence studies were carried out in 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixtures. As presented in Table 1 and Fig. 4, the aminodiene **1** in 1,4-dioxane shows fluorescence bands at 426 and 476 nm; however, these bands shift to 438 and 492 nm, respec-

Fig. 4. Fluorescence spectra of **1** in 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures : % of water in 1,4-dioxane is (a) 0, (b) 10, (c) 20, (d) 30, (e) 40, (f) 50, (g) 60, (h) 70, (i) 80 and (j) 90.

tively, when **1** is taken in a binary mixture of 1,4-dioxane containing 90% water. Further, with increase in percentage of water in 1,4-dioxane, there is decrease in the intensity of the shorter wavelength fluorescence band (in 433–438 nm range) and increase in the intensity and red-shift in $\lambda_{f \max}$ of the longer wavelength band (in 467–492 nm range). When 10–20% water in 1,4-dioxane is present, the intensity of shorter wavelength fluorescence band is more as compared to that of the longer wavelength fluorescence band. Thus, in 1,4-dioxane-water binary mixture also two fluorescence bands are observed at 435–438 and 467–492 nm, depending on the relative permittivity of the medium. However, the variation of water amount from zero to 90% causes a red-shift of only 12 and 25 nm in the two fluorescence bands. On the other hand, a variation from *n*-heptane to 90% water in 1,4-dioxane while causes a red-shift of only 16 nm in the lower wavelength fluorescence, a red-shift of 70 nm is observed in the longer wavelength fluorescence. Thus, with increasing solvent polarity the long wavelength fluorescence band gets further red-shifted.

The excited state responsible for fluorescence in **1** has been further characterized by determining the excited state dipole moment change ($\Delta\mu$) using the Lippert-Mataga equation⁷ : $\bar{\nu}_a - \bar{\nu}_f = [2(\mu_e - \mu_g)^2/hca^3] [(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1) - (n^2 - 1)/(2n^2 + 1) + K]$, where $\bar{\nu}_a$ and $\bar{\nu}_f$ are the peak absorption and emission (steady-state fluorescence) per cen-

timer, $\mu_e - \mu_g = \Delta\mu$ is the change in the dipole moment with μ_e and μ_g being the dipole moment of the molecule in excited and ground state, h is the Planck constant, c the velocity of light, a the Onsager cavity radius, and ϵ and n are the dielectric constant and refractive index of the solvent, respectively. The Onsager cavity radius for **1** has been taken approximately as 9 Å, which is a value considered for similar compound, namely, 1-*p*-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)phenyl-4-*p*-nitrophenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene⁸. Based on this analysis, the $\Delta\mu$ for **1** was found to be 18 D, which is similar to other donor-acceptor dienes^{6a,b}. It may, however, be pointed out that the $\Delta\mu$ value obtained here is only an approximate value due to the very approximate nature of the Onsager's radius taken for the aminodiene **1**.

These absorption, excitation and emission spectral data reveal the non-polar nature of the ground state and the polar nature of the singlet excited state of **1**. The solvent polarity dependent fluorescence of the aminodiene can thus be explained in terms of the involvement of initially prepared locally excited state and the intramolecular charge transfer excited state, which is polar in nature due to excited state charge transfer process. The intramolecular charge transfer can occur between the amino group (donor) and the dienyl moiety (acceptor). Thus, the shorter and longer wavelength fluorescence emissions of **1** can be attributed to the planar locally excited state and the planar intramolecular charge transfer excited states, respectively. The intramolecular charge transfer excited state is expected to be stabilized in a polar medium, giving fluorescence emission at a longer wavelength. The planar locally excited (PLE) state and the planar intramolecular charge transfer (PICT) excited state can be in solvent polarity controlled equilibrium (PLE $\rightleftharpoons$ PICT), which decides the appearance of the fluorescence bands of **1** in a given solvent. The PICT excited state can originate from the locally excited state and in solvents of very high polarity like DMF, the charge transfer state is highly stabilized and the fluorescence emission comes exclusively from this state.

The fluorescence emission behavior is also expected to be influenced by the solvent polarity energy level re-ordering of the lowest singlet excited states of the aminodiene. *trans*-Diphenylpolyenes belong to C_{2h} point group and their ground state is characterized by A_g symmetry while the electronically excited singlet π, π^* state can have either A_g^- and B_u^+ symmetry^{3c,h}. The B_u^+ excited state is believed to be associated with partial charge separation and ionic in nature, but the A_g^- excited state has covalent character. For 1,4-diphenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene (DPB), the energy gap between the two lowest excited singlet states of A_g^- and B_u^+ is small

and the exact order of the two excited states is not clearly understood. Since the two excited states are separated by only a small energy barrier, vibronic coupling and the solvent orientation with respect to the fluorophore are expected to influence the energy-level ordering of the two excited states, and hence the photophysical properties of the diene. It is possible that in relatively polar solvents, the fluorescence properties of **1** are due to the excited state having B_u^+ character. Due to low energy gap, the two excited states can undergo vibronic coupling and fluorescence from both the excited states can occur. The longer wavelength fluorescence emission can be from the ionic B_u excited state, which can undergo charge transfer process resulting in the formation of intramolecular charge transfer excited state in polar medium.

Absorption and fluorescence studies of aminodiene 1 in microheterogeneous media of micelles: The uv-vis absorption and fluorescence emission studies of **1** were done in CTAB, SDS and Triton-X-100 at three different concentration [pre-micellar concentration (1.0×10^{-3} to 1.0×10^{-4} M), critical micellar concentration (CMC, 1.0×10^{-2}

Table 2. Uv-vis and fluorescence emission spectral data for 1-*p*-aminophenyl-4-phenylbuta-1*E*,3*E*-diene (**1**) in CTAB, SDS and Triton-X-100*

Surfactant, [Conc.] M	$\lambda_{ab \max}$ nm	$\lambda_{f \max}$ nm	$\lambda_{ex \max}$ nm	ϕ_f
At pre-micellar concentration :				
CTAB, [1.0×10^{-4}]	348	439, 482	331	0.017
SDS, [1.0×10^{-3}]	348	435, 485	337	0.019
Triton-X-100, [1.0×10^{-4}]	348	435, 483	339	0.016
At CMC :				
CTAB, [1.0×10^{-3}]	348	438, 491	341	0.011
SDS, [1.0×10^{-2}]	333	436, 474	335	0.022
Triton-X-100, [1.0×10^{-3}]	361	438, 476	363	0.056
At above CMC :				
CTAB, [1.0×10^{-2}]	359	438, 477	360	0.052
SDS, [1.0×10^{-1}]	348	431, 466	341	0.042
Triton-X-100, [1.0×10^{-2}]	362	438, 473	360	0.080

* Explanation same as in Table 1.

to 1.0×10^{-3} M) and above micellar concentrations (1.0×10^{-1} to 1.0×10^{-2} M), of the surfactants, and the data are given in Table 2. At pre-micellar concentrations, no significant change is observed in the $\lambda_{ab \max}$ and $\lambda_{f \max}$ of the aminodiene. However, at CMC and above micellar concentration, the aminodiene shows considerable change in its $\lambda_{ab \max}$ and $\lambda_{f \max}$. With increasing micellar concentration, i.e. from CMC to above micellar concentration, there is a decrease in the longer wavelength $\lambda_{f \max}$ of **1** in CTAB

Fig. 5. Fluorescence spectra of **1** in CTAB at (a) pre-micelle concentration, (b) critical micelle concentration and (c) above micelle concentration.

Fig. 6. Fluorescence spectra of **1** in SDS at (a) pre-micelle concentration, (b) critical micelle concentration and (c) above micelle concentration.

Fig. 7. Fluorescence spectra of **1** in Triton-X-100 at (a) pre-micelle concentration, (b) critical micelle concentration and (c) above micelle concentration.

and SDS. As shown in Figs. 5–7, the aminodiene **1** shows two fluorescence bands in all the micelles, though the bands

are not as prominent in neutral Triton-X-100 as in ionic CTAB and SDS micelles. The two fluorescence emission bands clearly appear at the CMC of SDS. At CMC in CTAB micelles, the longer wavelength fluorescence band of **1** is slightly red-shifted as compared to at other two concentrations of the surfactant. In SDS and in Triton-X-100 micelles, however, the red-shifted fluorescence emission of **1** is observed at lower surfactant concentration and at CMC the bands are slightly blue-shifted. While in SDS, the two fluorescence bands that appear clearly, in Triton-X-100 the two bands are not very well separated. Thus, the fluorescence emission spectrum of **1** is most affected in SDS. In general, the $\lambda_{f\max}$ of **1** is red-shifted in CTAB as compared to that in SDS and Triton-X-100 micelles at CMC. The micellar charge-dependent shift in the $\lambda_{f\max}$ of **1** in various micelles shows that the aminodiene occupies interfacial region of the micelles, where the amino group of **1** is expected to interact differently with the head-groups, counter-ion and the bound water molecules in the micelle. As far Φ_f of **1** in micelles is concerned, below pre-micellar concentration, it fluoresces with almost similar efficiency in the three surfactants. However, at CMC and at above micellar concentration, the Φ_f of the aminodiene increases with the highest fluorescence efficiency in neutral Triton-X-100 micelles. This behavior is similar to that observed in the organic solvents in which with increase in solvent polarity there is a decrease in the Φ_f (Table 1).

An idea of the dielectric constant (ϵ) values could give information about the micropolarity of the micellar domain in which the aminodiene is intercalated. Therefore, ϵ values of different micelles constituted with **1** were calculated by comparing the $\lambda_{f\max}$ of **1** in different micelles to that obtained in 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures, for which the ϵ values are known⁹. The ϵ value of the intercalation site of **1** in various surfactant solutions determined this way are as follows: $\epsilon = 64$ in SDS/CTAB/Triton-X-100 at pre-micellar concentration; $\epsilon = 75, 25$ and 10 in CTAB, SDS and Triton-X-100, respectively, at CMC; and $\epsilon = 10, 5$ and 10 in CTAB, SDS and Triton-X-100, respectively, at above micellar concentration. Thus, at CMC, aminodiene **1** occupies relatively more polar region of the micelles of cationic surfactant CTAB. However, in anionic SDS micelles, it occupies a relatively less polar site, while in neutral Triton-X-100 micelles the aminodiene gets located in a relatively non-polar domain of the micelle. Further, at higher surfactant concentrations (i.e. above CMC), the aminodiene occupies a rather non-polar regions in the micelles of all the three surfactants. A schematic diagram depicting the typical intercalation of **1** in the micelles is shown in Fig. 8, wherein the polar amino group can be located towards the head re-

Fig. 8. A schematic representation of the intercalation of aminodiene **1** in the interfacial domain of the micelles.

gion, and dienyl moiety containing the phenyl ring can be incorporated between hydrophobic alkyl chains of the micelles. The aminodiene is anchored in the micelles by hydrogen bond and hydrophobic interactions. The polar amino group can interact with the head group as well as with the structured bound water molecules in the Stern layer¹⁰ and the dienyl moiety can interact hydrophobically with the alkyl chains of the surfactants. However, variations in the orientation and interaction of **1** in different micelles are possible, and the actual solubilization site and orientation would depend on the concentration and the type of surfactant used.

In conclusion, it can be said that the aminodiene **1** exhibits solvent-polarity dependent fluorescence emission, which can be attributed to the initially prepared planar locally excited state in non-polar solvents and intramolecular charge transfer planar, dipolar excited state in polar solvents. The aminodiene **1** in non-polar medium fluoresces more efficiently as compared to in the polar medium. In microheterogeneous media of micelles the aminodiene **1** gets intercalated in the interfacial regions of the micelles and shows micellar charge-dependent shift in $\lambda_{f \max}$ and fluoresces more efficiently than in organic solvents or in 1,4-dioxane-water mixtures. However, with increase in surfactant concentration, the aminodiene occupies relatively less-polar regions of the micelles. Thus, in contrast to nitro-substituted diphenylbutadienes, the amino-substituted diphenylbutadiene in polar medium exhibits fluorescence from planar intramolecular charge transfer excited states and not from the conformationally relaxed twisted intramolecular charge transfer excited state. This study has brought out interesting features of the excited state structure and dynamics of linear polyenes and shows the importance of charge transfer excited states in the photoprocesses of linear polyenes. It also gives new directions for designing fluorescence probes for investigating the microenvironment of organized assemblies.

Experimental

The chemicals used in the synthesis of aminodiene **1** and other chemicals such as quinine sulfate, surfactant SDS, CTAB and Triton-X-100, and the organic solvents were obtained from SRL Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai and Spectrochem, Mumbai (India). All the chemicals were used without further purification. However, the organic solvents were dried and distilled prior to their use by standard procedures¹¹.

M.p.s. were determined on a Veego apparatus and are uncorrected. Uv-vis spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer, IR spectra (KBr) on an Impact 400 Nicolet FTIR spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) using TMS as internal standard on a Varian 300 MHz FT NMR spectrometer available at the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentations Center, I.I.T. Bombay. Steady state fluorescence measurements were made on a DM1B microprocessor controlled Spex-112 Fluorolog spectrofluorimeter having slit width of 1 and 1.5 nm for excitation and emission monochromators, respectively. The quantum yield of fluorescence (Φ_f) were obtained against quinine sulfate in 1 N H₂SO₄ (Φ_f , 0.545) as standard¹². Surfactants were dissolved in double-distilled and deionized water for micelle preparation. For solubilization of aminodiene **1** in surfactant solutions, appropriate amount of aminodiene **1** was added to the aqueous surfactant solution and the mixture was thoroughly shaken or briefly sonicated to get a clear solution of the aminodiene in the surfactants.

1-p-Nitrophenyl-4-phenylbuta-1E,3E-diene: It was prepared by condensation of cinnamaldehyde and phosphonate ester of *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide as described earlier^{6b}. Further reduction of the nitro group in the nitrodiene with stannous chloride in ethanol gave the desired aminodiene **1**. In a typical reduction procedure, a mixture of 1-*p*-nitrophenyl-4-phenylbuta-1E,3E-diene (0.006 mol) and stannous chloride (0.048 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC and after disappearance of the starting material, the reaction mixture was cooled to 0° and poured in ice-cold water. It was made slightly basic with dil. ammonia, extracted with ethyl acetate (4 × 50 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. Evaporation of ethyl acetate under vacuo yielded a yellow colored product which was further purified by column chromatography using neutral alumina: yield 85%, m.p. 150–151°, $\lambda_{\max}$ (1,4-dioxane) 356 nm (ϵ , 38400 M dm⁻³ cm⁻¹); $\nu_{\max}$ (cm⁻¹) 3425, 3341, 3209 (NH₂), 1597 (C=C), 989 (C-H def for *trans*-alkene); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) δ 3.74 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.58 (1H, d, *J* 15.11 Hz, H₂N-C₆H₄-CH=), 6.62–6.67 (3H, H₂N-C₆H₄- and C₆H₅-CH=), 6.78 (1H, dd, *J* 14.97/10.44 Hz, H₂N-C₆H₄-

CH=CH-), 6.93 (1H, dd, *J* 15.23/10.44 Hz, C₆H₅-CH=CH-), 7.17–7.33 (5H, m, C₆H₅-), 7.42 (2H, dd, *J* 7.98/1.93 Hz, H₂N-C₆H₄-).

The solutions of aminodiene **1** were prepared and handled under protective dim red light condition in the laboratory.

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